

Unhackable Quantum Internet: A Revolutionary Innovation of the 21st Century

Dr. A. Shaji George¹, A. S. Hovan George², Digvijay Pandey³

Masters IT Solutions, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India^{1,2}

Department of Technical Education (Government of U.P), India.³

Abstract: The concept of the quantum internet shall be to profoundly improve Internet technology by allowing quantum communication amongst any two points on Earth. Quantum technology, as well as research, will open up the door to all types of new possibilities and opportunities. Some of those possibilities include the speed of communications, Although the first implementations of small-scale quantum networks are anticipated in the foreseeable future, scaling those networks presents enormous challenges for fields such as physics, computer science as well as engineering. This has important implications for a wide variety of fields from the weather forecast to healthcare research as well as the development of Artificial Intelligence, not to mention that the previously known effect on cybersecurity and the ability to break existing encryption methods. At this moment, we are convinced that the quantum Internet will have the ability to do incredible things, considerably faster than the traditional Internet. The great advantage of quantum communication is that it is much more secure than everything else. The internet could look ahead to a bright future with the new quantum technology hacking proof exchange of information as well as superfast data processing is going to become possible. Such a significant breakthrough will provide them with a competitive edge in a hopeful technology and opens a new universe of innovations and unlimited opportunities. In this paper, we offer an overview of benefits anticipated on the Quantum Internet. In this paper, the author presents the fundamental ideas of quantum physics, describes the concepts of quantum repeaters, and the mechanism of a quantum Internet. Particular attention is given not just to the technical problems implicated, but additionally to the potential impact on society. The purpose of this paper is to provide a straightforward understanding regarding Quantum Internet as well as how it developed, and the advantages of Quantum Internet.

Keywords: Quantum Networks, Artificial Intelligence, Qubits, Quantum Internet, Quantum key distribution (QKD), Quantum Computing, Quantum Communications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The traditional Internet has been continuously expanding ever since it first turned out to be commercially prevalent during the early 1990s. It basically comprises a huge number of end-nodes e.g., laptops, Desktops, network servers, mobile phones, tablets, which are connected with routers. Endpoint nodes are running applications that offer some added value to service for end-users like the processing and transmission of data, voice, and video. The physical connection between the different nodes through the internet comprises DSL-Digital Subscriber Lines, Optical fiber, etc. Bits will be transmitted across the Internet in packets. The internet is having a revolutionary effect on our world. Research and experiments have picked up over the past few years for the development of the Quantum Internet. The concept of a quantum internet is to deliver radically new internet technology through facilitating quantum communication among any two points on the Planet. The quantum internet will, in cooperation with the traditional internet which we have now link the quantum information processors in order to attain unmatched capabilities which are proven to be unfeasible by using just traditional information. Like with any fundamentally innovative technology, it is difficult to predict every use of the prospective quantum internet. Though, numerous major applications have now been identified, clock synchronization, secure identification, as well as secure communication, broadening the baseline of telescopes, attaining efficient agreement on distributed data, rapid savings in communication, quantum sensor networks, and safe access to remote quantum computers within the cloud. Central to every application is the potential of a quantum internet to communicate quantum bits (qubits) that are radically different than classical bits. While classical bits can take on just two values, 0 or 1, qubits may be in the superposition of being 0 and 1 at the very same time. Furthermore, qubits may be entangled with one another, which leads to the connections over huge distances that are far more powerful than remains possible with classical information. The Qubits likewise can't be copied, and any effort to achieve this could be detected. This functionality makes qubits perfectly suited for security applications while at the same time it makes the transmission of qubits need completely new ideas and technology. Swift experimental progress has been made in recent days which has given the first basic quantum networks within the reach, emphasizing

timeliness as well as the need for an integrated framework for quantum internet scientists. Quantum Internet will be providing essential advantages like better end-user as well as network security. A Quantum Internet shall have the end-nodes, which can be linked by quantum repeaters or routers. The quantum end-nodes are going to also run additional value applications. Basic physical connections between the different nodes in the Quantum Internet are likely to be mainly optical fiber as well as free-space optics. Optical links are especially useful since light (photons) is highly suitable for physically encoding qubits. In contrast to the classical Internet, qubits, as well as not classical bits or packets, are anticipated to be transmitted through the Quantum Internet because of the fundamental physics. Quantum Internet will function in accordance with distinctive physical principles like quantum superposition, entanglement as well as teleportation. Quantum Internet is not expected to substitute the traditional Internet. On the other hand, Quantum Internet will be incorporated into the traditional Internet to create a new hybrid Internet. The whole process of incorporating the Quantum Internet with the traditional Internet is comparable to, although with more profound consequences, the entire process of launching any Innovative communication and networking model into the current Internet. The purpose of this paper is to offer a shared understanding and structure of applications as well as use instances for the Quantum Internet.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In the recent period, technological innovations, as well as technological advancement, play an important role. The main aim of the research paper is to discuss the quantum internet and the expected changes in the Industry because of Quantum computing which can change the world. It can transform medicine, break encryption as well as revolutionise communications and AI. The Un-hackable quantum internet revolutionary innovation is expected to re-shape the world's economy. This research aims to find out the information communicated in preliminary media and publication coverage of Quantum Internet. The current research will be based upon the following objectives.

- To give a brief description about the Quantum Internet.
- An Explanation about the Quantum Repeaters.
- An analysis of the Mechanism of Quantum Internet.
- How building and Scaling Quantum Internet is a Challenging Effort.
- Information that can be exchanged with Quantum.
- Why Quantum Communications is more Secure.
- Is Quantum Internet a substitute for the current Internet Infrastructure.
- To visualize new possibilities for Quantum software developers to create new applications.
- What else can we do with Quantum Internet.
- The Challenging task of building Quantum Internet.
- The limitations of Quantum Internet.

III.ABOUT QUANTUM INTERNET

The quantum internet is a network that will allow quantum devices to exchange certain information inside an environment that uses the rules of quantum mechanics. Theoretically, this will make it possible to give the quantum internet unparalleled capabilities which are impossible to be carried out by the present web-enabled applications. In quantum, the data may be encoded in the form of qubits, which could be created in quantum devices such as a quantum processor or the quantum computer. The quantum internet, in simple words, will entail sending qubits over a network of multiple quantum devices that are physically separated. Fundamentally, all of this will happen owing to the strange characteristics which are unique to quantum states. This may sound comparable to the standard internet. However, sending qubits over a quantum channel, instead of a classical one, effectively means tapping into the behaviours of particles once taken at their smallest scale known as quantum states, that have caused delight as well as dismay amongst scientists for decades. The laws of quantum physics, that underpin the manner in which data will be transmitted in the quantum internet, are nothing short of strange. Furthermore, they are strange, contradictory, and on occasion even apparently supernatural. Therefore, to comprehend how the quantum ecosystem of the internet two operates, you may want to forget all you know about classical computing. Not enough of the quantum internet shall remind you of your preferred internet browser.

IV. QUANTUM REPEATERS

In space, photons are able to travel for hundreds and hundreds of kilometers with a tiny probability of getting lost. It is a luxury that does not apply to the fiber. For example, a photon source that releases ten billion photons each second, along with a fiber connection where a bit under one out of twenty photons gets dropped each kilometer. After 500

kilometers the rate has fallen to nearly one photon arriving each second. After passing 1000 kilometers of fiber there will be such a huge fall in the rate that you may not even be able to gauge any photon in your very own lifetime no longer after 1000 kilometers of fiber nearly one photon shall arrive every 300 years. Hence, the signal will need to be refreshed.

Fig:1 Quantum Repeaters

Fig. 1 Quantum Repeaters

Rejuvenating the signal with classical nodes

Through a pre-quantum network, such as those in Japan and China, this represents the job of traditional nodes. At the node, the photons which arrive are being collected as well as their state is measured. Then, fresh photons at the right state will be sent towards the following node through the chain.

The next phase: quantum repeaters

In phases beyond the pre-quantum network, the objective is to rejuvenate the signal with a different type of node a quantum repeater. True quantum repeaters have still not been achieved so far, but in the foreseeable future, the foundation for such repeaters is going to be put on the Dutch quantum network. To understand how quantum repeaters work, it is essential to understand a completely different idea first, quantum teleportation.

Fig:2 Quantum Network

Fig. 2 Quantum Network

V. THE MECHANISM OF QUANTUM INTERNET

Quantum key distribution technology is in its initial stages. The normal way to create Quantum key distribution at present comprises transmitting the qubits in a one-directional path to the receiver, via optic-fibre cables although those considerably restrict the effectiveness of the present protocol. Qubits can simply get lost or dispersed in a fibre-optic cable, meaning that the quantum signals are very error-prone, as well as struggle to travel lengthy distances. Present experiments are restricted to a range of hundreds of kilometers. There is an alternative solution, and it is the one which underlines the quantum internet to control an additional property of quantum, known as entanglement, for communication between the two devices. Once two qubits interact with each other and become entangled, they are sharing particular properties that rely on one another. At the Same Time, the qubits are to be found in an entangled state, any alteration to one particle in the pair will lead to changes to the other, even though they are separate physically. The state of the initial qubit can be "read" by examining the behavior of its entangled counterpart. And within the framework of quantum communication, entanglement can in effect, teleport certain information from one qubit to its entangled remaining half, without the need to have a physical channel connecting the two throughout the transmission.

VI. BUILDING AND SCALING QUANTUM INTERNET IS A CHALLENGING EFFORT

Building and scaling quantum Internet is a remarkable endeavor, that requires continuous and collaborative efforts in physics, computer science, as well as engineering to achieve success. The planned stages of growth will help to facilitate interdisciplinary communication through reviewing what we could really want to accomplish as well as providing standards equally to protocol design and software development and the hardware deployments all through experimental physics and engineering. While it is difficult to predict what the precise components of a potential future quantum internet are going to be, it is probable that we are going to look at the beginning of the very first multinode quantum networks in the next few years. Such development brings the thrilling chance to test all the concepts and functionalities that have so far only happen on paper and could indeed be the dawn of a potential future large scale quantum internet.

VII. INFORMATION THAT CAN BE EXCHANGED WITH QUANTUM

The key to quantum communication is the simple fact that qubits, that enables you to use the fundamental laws of quantum mechanics, act completely differently to classical bits. As it encodes data, a classical bit will be able to effectively just be one of two states. The same way as a light switch will have to be either on or off, and just as a cat will have to be either dead or alive, thus a bit must be either 0 or 1. Not quite so much with qubits. On the Contrary, qubits are superposed, they maybe 0 and 1 at the same time, in a special quantum state that does not exist within the classical world. It is a bit as though you can be both on the left-hand side as well as the right-hand side of your couch, at exactly the same time. The paradox is that the simple act of measuring a qubit indicates that it is allocated a state. A measured qubit automatically drops from its dual state, while at the same time is changed to 0 or 1, in the same way as a classical bit. The entire phenomenon is known as superposition, as well as lies at the core of quantum mechanics. Naturally, qubits could not be used to transmit the kind of data that we are familiar with, such as emails as well as WhatsApp messages. Although, the odd behavior of qubits is opening up enormous opportunities in some other, more special applications.

VIII. QUANTUM COMMUNICATIONS IS MORE SECURE

One of the most interesting avenues that scientists, equipped with qubits, are studying, is security. In classical communications, most data are secured by way of distributing a common key to the sender and the recipient, and then by using this common key to encrypt the message. A receiver will be able to use their key to decode the data at their end. The security of most classical communication now is based upon an algorithm used for creating keys which is difficult for hackers to break, although not impossible. This is the reason why scientists are looking at creating this communication method as quantum. The idea is at the core of an evolving field of cybersecurity dubbed Quantum Key distribution. Quantum Key Distribution operates by having one of the two parties encrypt the piece of classical data through encoding the cryptography key onto qubits. The transmitter then sends those qubits to another person, the person that measures the qubits in order to get the key values. Measuring will cause the state of the qubit to collapse although it is the value that is read out during the measuring process which is essential. The qubit, in a sense, is just there to transport the key value. The most important thing is that Quantum key distribution means is that it is easy to find out if a third party has spied on the qubits throughout the transmission because the intruder would have resulted in the key to collapse just by looking at it. In the event that a hacker was looking at the qubits at any given time while they

were being transmitted, this would automatically alter the state of the qubits. A spy will inevitably leave a sign of spying and that is why cryptographers claim that quantum key distribution is secure.

IX. IS QUANTUM INTERNET A SUBSTITUTE FOR THE CURRENT INTERNET INFRASTRUCTURE

Quantum internet will not replace the current internet but remain an additional function. The traditional internet as the ordinary internet is sometimes referred to will continue to exist. Quantum Internet will begin being implemented for particular use cases by the government and the financial institutions to maintain backbone connections safe. It is anticipated that large organizations will depend on the quantum internet to protect the data. Firstly, it will connect the data centers as well as other important back-end sites. Later it is going to be filtered down in phases, ultimately achieving individual residences, however, that individual consumers are going to continue to use the traditional internet at least for some time. By making quantum internet widely accessible to the public, some consider that it may need to exist in a clientless form in the cloud application.

X. NEW POSSIBILITIES FOR QUANTUM SOFTWARE DEVELOPERS TO CREATE NEW APPLICATIONS

We will define various stages of growth on the way to the full-blown quantum internet. We anticipate that such a classification will play an important role in directing and evaluating new progress and promoting the development of innovative applications by offering a common language and a reference structure for the different scientific and engineering fields involved. More sophisticated stages are characterized by a greater number of features and capabilities, thereby supporting more and more sophisticated application protocols. For every stage, we refer to some of the application protocols which are already known, and which can be achieved with the features provided in that phase. It is possible that a more straightforward protocol, or improved theoretical analysis, can be found in the foreseeable future that solves an identical task but remains less challenging in terms of the features. In parallel with the formidable emerging challenges in creating quantum internet into a reality, there is, therefore, a chance for quantum software developers to create protocols that can accomplish the task in a stage that could be implemented more simply. We recognize the appropriate parameters for every stage to create a common language among hardware and software developers. Lastly, we examine technological advancement in experimental physics, engineering, as well as computer science that is needed to achieve such phases.

Fig:3 Quantum Internet Industries and Application

Fig. 3 Quantum Internet Industries and Application

XI. WHAT ELSE CAN WE DO WITH QUANTUM INTERNET

What is the need for entanglement? Researchers could just find ways to enhance the typical form of QKD. Quantum repeaters, for instance, can go a long way in improving communication distance in optical fiber cables without needing

to go as far as to entangle qubits. That is to say with no accounting for the enormous potential that entanglement might have for additional applications. QKD is the most commonly talked-about instance of anything the quantum internet could accomplish since it is the most available application of this technology. However, security is a long way from being the one field that is causing enthusiasm amongst researchers. Quantum entanglement network meant for QKD can also be used, for instance, to offer a credible way to develop quantum clusters that have been created of entangled qubits located in various quantum devices. Researchers will not need an especially powerful chunk of quantum hardware to link to the quantum internet actually, just as a single-qubit processor can get the job done. Although by connecting together quantum devices which, while they stand, have restricted capabilities, researchers believe that they will be able to create a quantum supercomputer to exceed them all.

By linking several small quantum devices altogether, thus, the quantum internet could begin solving the issues that are currently difficult to achieve into a single quantum computer. This would include accelerating the exchange of huge quantities of data, and taking out large-scale sensing experiments in materials discovery, life sciences as well as astronomy. So, researchers are confident that we can derive the benefits of the quantum internet prior to tech giants like IBM and Google yet accomplish quantum dominance the time when a particular quantum computer is going to fix a problem that is problematic for a classical computer. IBM and Google's most sophisticated quantum computers presently have around fifty qubits, which is far less than is necessary to carry out the phenomenal calculations necessary to resolve the issues that quantum research plans to address. Instead, connecting such devices simultaneously through quantum entanglement can result in clusters having several thousands of qubits. For several researchers, establishing such computing power is actually the ultimate objective of the quantum internet project.

XII. THE CHALLENGING TASK OF BUILDING QUANTUM INTERNET

Although prior to any of that could happen scientists have to figure out how to create quantum internet and provided the oddness of quantum mechanics, it's not going to be simple. In the classical world it is possible to encode information and then save it and it does not deteriorate. In the quantum world, it is possible to encode information and it begins to deteriorate almost instantly. The other problem is that due to the fact that the quantity of energy that matches the quantum information is very low it's hard to prevent it from cooperating with the external world. At Present, in many instances quantum systems simply work at extremely low temperatures, another option is to work in the vacuum and pump all the air out of the system. To make quantum internet, all kinds of hardware which has not been built yet. Therefore, it is difficult to say at the moment precisely when a quantum internet is going to be up and running, although a Chinese researcher has predicted that it could occur as quickly as.

XIII. THE LIMITATIONS OF QUANTUM INTERNET

For the foreseeable destiny, the quantum net couldn't be used to trade facts inside the way that we currently do on our laptops. Imagining a generalized, mainstream quantum net could require waiting for many years (or greater) of technological advancements. As a great deal as scientists dream of the future of the quantum net, therefore, it's far not possible to draw parallels between the mission as it currently stands, and the way we browse the web each day. quite a few quantum conversation research nowadays is devoted to locating out how to best encode, compress and transmit information way to quantum states. Quantum states, of direction, are recognized for their notable densities, and scientists are assured that one node could teleport a terrific deal of records. however, the form of records that scientists are searching at sending over the quantum internet has little to do with starting an inbox and scrolling thru emails. and actually, replacing the classical internet isn't what technology has set out to do. alternatively, researchers are hoping that the quantum internet will take a seat next to the classical internet and would be used for more specialized packages. The quantum internet will perform obligations that can be carried out quicker on a quantum computer than on classical computers, or which might be too hard to carry out even at the high-quality supercomputers that exist nowadays.

XIV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have been discussing the quantum internet as well as its technological developments that encompass the fundamental concepts to comprehend quantum internet technology. In the future quantum, the internet shall exchange security based on different quantum key distribution algorithms and allows for networking of traditional as well as quantum nodes that are located remotely. Plans are in place to develop ultra-low loss photonic circuits as well as large-scale graph state photon generators in order to scale up the full optical quantum network-based internet. Researchers are just getting started with the concept of Quantum internet. A major breakthrough has been accomplished since the introduction of the quantum satellites that have reached QKD between the two remote ground stations, which has encouraged various research teams to speed up the attempts to build a full-driven quantum internet in the foreseeable future. Quantum networks, as well as many other inventions, which come from fundamental research in academia and laboratories, face technology transfer issues in spite of their tremendous potential to enhance the skills

and benefits of society. Partnerships between the governments and big technology corporations will become more and more needed in the development and deployment of such technologies into different systems. Largely the education sector will be required to educate prospective professionals as well as industrial and technological sectors will have to understand, support, and create new products which use quantum technologies. Quantum technologies have just started to open the gates to a new age. This paper can also be used as a preliminary text to individuals who are interested in getting to know the practical applications of the Quantum Internet. Ultimately, it is anticipated that this paper is going to help guide additional research and the development of Quantum Internet.

REFERENCES

- [1]. ZDNet- What is the quantum internet? Everything you need to know about the weird future of quantum networks-By Daphne Leprince-Ringuet – September 3,2020.
- [2]. Cyber Talk – Quantum Internet: Fast forward into the future <https://www.cybertalk.org/2020/10/23/quantum-internet-fast-forward-into-the-future/>
- [3]. Quantum internet: A vision for the road ahead-BY STEPHANIE WEHNER, DAVID ELKOUSS, RONALD HANSON- SCIENCE19 OCT 2018 <https://science.sciencemag.org/content/362/6412/eaam9288>
- [4]. Howstuffworks- tech - We're Getting Closer to the Quantum Internet, But What Is It BY PATRICK J. KIGER MAR 30, 2020.
- [5]. QUANTUMXCHANGE- <https://quantumxc.com/is-quantum-communication-faster-than-the-speed-of-light>
- [6]. BBN TIMES-Ahmed Banafa-30.11.2020 <https://www.bbntimes.com/science/quantum-internet-explained>
- [7]. 101-Tech-By Malaika Ashfaq <https://www.101tech.info/what-is-the-quantum-internet/>
- [8]. ITPro- The quantum internet is on its way- Nicole Kobie 22 Mar 2021.